

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE IN TEACHING AND LEARNING FOREIGN LANAGUAGES

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Good secondary – specialized educational institutions strive to create an atmosphere where students feel cared about, and feel free to express their individuality. Is this social acceptance? It is a part of the equation in social acceptance. B1 level students strive to be accepted and to become part of a group. How is this accomplished when it is a daily challenge to communicate?

Perhaps past teachers' social behavior, instructional behavior, and teaching tactics result in poor classroom etiquette that created a barrier for communicating with English language learners. Thornberg (2008) suggested that teachers with poor classroom etiquette were dismissed because it was ineffective communication and social skills.

Some educators used bad language and unethical decision-making in the classroom and displayed behaviors that were not viewed as tradition or as school culture. Where poor etiquette exist, students cannot achieve the goals needed to receive grade level promotions and graduate certifications (Worrell, 2008).

According to Orosco and Klingner (2010), educators with limited skills and training were not prepared to instruct English language learners. Too little preparation before entering the teaching profession limits the expertness of curriculum content and pedagogical skills to instruct learners (Tikly & Barrett, 2009). Honigsfeld and Dove(2008) suggested that to have a positive influence on the educational environment, classroom teachers, administrators, and those instructing English language learners must have intercultural communication skills, social skills, and training in educating English language learners. Educators must be equipped with the ability to use appropriate resources and technology to assist English language learners (Morgan, 2012). Educators who do not update knowledge and skill with continued education may not apply current skills and knowledge to help English language learners (Freidus et al., 2009).

A name is an important part of a person's identity. When people are called by their name, it gives them a sense of self-worth. Studies by Manning (1994) have

indicated that names definitely affect how people function because of the impact on one's self-worth.

Students are happy when teachers have taken the time to learn each student's name. Sometimes teachers have the difficult task of remembering and saying very unusual names. ELL students are very cooperative in assisting teachers with the correct pronunciation of their names because it is part of a student's identity. This seems like such a simple thing, but knowing a student's name and pronouncing it correctly adds to social acceptance.

According to Schirmeer and Twiss (1996), guidelines for teachers of ELL students include:

- (a) never make assumptions,
 - (b) ask the students,
 - (c) never give the student a new name, and
 - (d) remember that the structure and use of names varies among cultural groups.
- Research by Freeman and Freeman (2000) found that one such obstacle is the need to create an environment in the classroom that is welcoming for multiple languages. Other obstacles include inclusion, communication with other students, class size, and following the state-mandated curriculum.

The majority of teachers are not trained in linguistic levels, cultural diversity issues, or the learning styles that produce successful results for ELL students. Still ELL students are placed in their classrooms due to mainstreaming laws. In these classrooms, it is common for LEP students to feel isolated and not part of the group. This is due to a lack of social acceptance, and it does interrupt academic success.

Research compiled by Carrasquillo and Rodriquez (1997) suggested principles for guiding mainstream classrooms for ELL students. The first principle states that mainstreaming should provide a full range of educational opportunities to all students. In addition, the second principle requires providing opportunities for ELL students to interact socially with English proficient peers. The third principle includes opportunities for ELL students to function effectively in groups after successful instructional strategies are clarified, and the fourth principle remains loyal to mainstreaming. The fourth principle explains that the practice should provide opportunities for regular education teachers to consider the language demands for all students (Carrasquillo& Rodriquez).

These principles provide additional data for incorporating teaching strategies that will be adaptable for all learning styles, including ELL students. The aforementioned principles should help to promote social acceptance within the

academic classroom. Inclusion and instruction within the mainstream classroom are used in public education throughout Georgia for students with special needs. ELL students fall under the special needs group, and ELL students are therefore mainstreamed into regular education classrooms (Hamayan & Damico, 1991). Mainstreaming is considered inclusion, and it is the regular education teacher's responsibility to ensure that the environment is welcoming. Class size is an integral part of inclusion, and it has to be a major consideration when scheduling classes for ELL students.

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